

A-Priori Error Estimator based Hierarchical p Adaptivity Scheme for Acoustic Problems

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ABSTRACT

In this paper the development of efficient computational method for Helmholtz equation is presented. Here we solve the Helmholtz equation in the frequency domain, applying hierarchical finite element approximation with generalized Duffy transformation based on unstructured meshes [4], where both pressure field and geometry are independently approximated with arbitrary and heterogeneous polynomial order. We demonstrate the implementation and performance of the numerical approach by benchmark problems, especially under pollution effects, which also validate the accuracy and efficiency of an object oriented a priori error estimator through numerical assessments.

Key Words: p adaptivity scheme; Hierarchical basis; Lobatto shape functions; Duffy transformation; A priori error estimator

1. Introduction

It is widely accepted that acoustic problems have vast range of uses in different physical applications, in the context of microfluidic object subject to high frequency SAW (surface acoustic waves), the applications encompass disease diagnostics, biochemical analysis, drug delivery, aid to build the lab-on-chip system. However, the modelling of high frequency application is difficult in practical situations due to capacity of numerical methods.

The main idea of error analysis is to find the optimised numerical scheme allowed fast frequency sweep acoustic applications. There are mainly two subjects under the category of error estimator: a priori and a posteriori. The a priori error estimator is the estimation of the exact error before we reach the approximation solution which based on known information about the exact solutions in object specific norms. The major drawback of a posterior error estimator is that it requires the finite element solution calculated before the estimated error.

Proposed finite element technology is implemented in open-source finite element University of Glasgow in-house parallel computational code, MoFEM (Mesh Oriented Finite Element Method) [2].

2. Mathematical formulation

Let Ω be a domain in \mathbb{R}^3 with smooth boundary and outward unit normal n . In the assumption of time harmonic wave, the steady part of the wave equation for the propagation of acoustic waves in an isotropic, ideal medium is described as

$$\nabla \cdot \nabla \Phi(\mathbf{r}) + k^2 \Phi(\mathbf{r}) = f(\mathbf{r}) \text{ in } \Omega \quad (1a)$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \Phi(\mathbf{r})}{\partial n} + i\sigma \Phi \right) = g \text{ on } \Gamma \quad (1b)$$

where the variation of $f(\mathbf{r})$ in (1a) can be regarded as a point source of acoustic wave. Eq (1b) exhibits the mixed boundary condition (MBC) with material constant σ and acoustic energy g , which can be used to describe any BCs by modifying the parameters. The example of benchmark problem with plane wave impinging on a sound hard sphere are shown in Figure 1 where diffraction of energy can be observed.

(a) Real potential (b) Imaginary potential (c) Real potential (d) Imaginary potential

Figure 1: Sound hard and soft sphere scatterer Φ_S , where $a = 0.5$, $r = 3$, $k = 10$, $no.DOFs = 243337$, and approximation order $p = 5$.

3. Generalized Duffy transformation for simplex

The accurate higher order Gauss points and weights lying within the element domain are extremely difficult to derive for simplex geometry. The difficulty of searching quadrature rules generally leads to well known problem of finding the zeros or minima of high-order multi-variate polynomials, as well as general limitation of p order below 7 .

Figure 2: Illustration of Duffy transformation for simplex (a) 2D (b) 3D

In 1982, Duffy introduced an integration techniques which can increasing the accuracy of integration while eliminates the integrand with a $\frac{1}{r}$ singularity on vertex. In this paper, we present a special case of generalised Duffy transformation which collapse the hexahedron to tetrahedron directly by changes the transformation to: $Q^3 \square(u, v, w) \rightarrow \mathcal{T}^3 \Delta(x, y, z) : x = u^\beta v w, y = x v (1 - z) = u^\beta v (1 - w), z = x (1 - y) = u^\beta (1 - v)$ [3]. In this paper, we employ generalized Duffy transformation to integrate simplex element for volume and surfaces, it guarantees the exactness of integrand with arbitrary polynomial orders.

4. Hierarchical Lobatto basis for tetrahedron

The difficulty arisen in acoustic problem is the increasing of frequency causes the grows of condition number of system matrix, which is $\kappa = \|\mathbf{A}\| \cdot \|\mathbf{A}^{-1}\|$ for system of linear equations $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}$. Where $\|\mathbf{A}\|$ can represents any specific norms (typically L_2). The quantity of memory required to store and factorize the system matrix also related to the conditioning of matrix. The reason of keeping condition number relative low is to maintain a stable and rigorous solution particular for large problems with huge size of system matrix using iterative solvers. The Legendre basis functions are:

$$L_n(\bar{\zeta}) = \frac{2n-1}{n} \bar{\zeta} L_{n-1}(\bar{\zeta}) - \frac{n-1}{n} L_{n-2}(\bar{\zeta}), \text{ for } n = 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (2)$$

where $-1 \leq \bar{\zeta} \leq 1$ for the first order functions, $L_0(\bar{\zeta}) = 1$ and $L_1(\bar{\zeta}) = \bar{\zeta}$. Legendre basis has orthogonality property in L_2 . The Lobatto basis functions are derived from modified integrated Legendre basis, thus inherited the hierarchical orthogonal property. The p_{th} order Lobatto basis for edges are computed based on $p - 1_{th}$ Legendre basis:

$$l_i(\zeta) = \sqrt{i - \frac{1}{2}} \int_{-1}^{\zeta} L_{i-1}(\bar{\zeta}) d\bar{\zeta}, \quad \text{for } i = 2, 3, \dots, p \quad (3)$$

for $L_i(\zeta)$ is the Legendre basis of order i . Its orthogonality property up to first order derivative in H_1 can delivery coarser stiffness matrix together with the Duffy transformation of Gauss quadrature. Intuitively, they together lead to better conditioning for sparse system matrix with high wavenumbers [4]. Figure 3 reveals the fact that hierarchical Lobatto basis is better conditioned than the Legendre basis especially for high frequencies.

Figure 3: Lobatto basis versus Legendre basis coupled with Duffy transformation, condition number against number of polynomial orders. Impinging sound hard sphere in 3D with $r = 4$, $a = 0.5$

5. A simple object oriented error estimator

In the basic assumption of relation between 1D element and higher dimensional element, error incurs from higher order element can be estimated from error in 1D element. In essence, the error indicator estimates the average of errors occurred in each element from a given mesh. The detailed implementation procedures are depicted in Chart 4.

The efficiency of adaptivity scheme can be improved by calculate the criterion of $\chi_{kh} = k'h'$ value corresponding to the best polynomial order p , and put into a table in the premise of pre-defined error level η . Consequently, the value of kh in each element is compared with the criterion value χ_{kh} , if actual $kh < \chi_{kh}$, the best p corresponding to χ_{kh} is employed.

The piecewise H^1 actual error is calculated on the computational domain for benchmark problem in Figure 4. The dispersion error caused by phase lag is a global effect that builds up itself over the whole computational domain. Figure 4b identifies the fact that there are large parts of errors occurred around the boundary of scatterer, the infinite domain, and along the propagation direction. The former can be sufficiently eliminated through p adaptivity algorithm as shown in 4b (p order: blue = 3, cyan = 4, green = 5, red = 6.), where the latter contributed by the dispersion errors can only be alleviated. Nevertheless, these dispersion errors can be minimised by hierarchical shape functions of Lobatto basis through p adaptivity, in such a way that the phase accuracy of higher order element is greater than lower order element with approximately same total no. of $DOFs$. The total relative H^1 error is approximately

Algorithm 1 Pseudo Code : A Priori Error Indicator

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1: procedure EVERY ELEMENT IN COMPUTATIONAL DOMAIN
2:    $h_a = \frac{\sum_i^6 h_i}{6}$   $\leftarrow$  average length of edges
3:    $k \leftarrow$  wavenumber
4:   set :  $p_{node} = 1$ 
5:   set : error = 0
6:   set :  $p_{max} = 10$ 
7:   loop
8:   for  $ii = 1; ii < p_{max}; ii++$ 
9:     solve 1D acoustic problem based on  $h_a$  and  $k$ 
10:    set : new error
11:    if error > expected error level ( $ii$ ) then
12:      increase  $p_{edge}, p_{face}, p_{interior}$ 
13:    else
14:      break loop;
15:   end
16:   store  $p$  for each entities, and set the polynomial orders.
17: start calculation.

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(a) Flow chart

H1 error before p adaptivity

H1 error after p adaptivity

(b) Predicted optimal p order

Figure 4: a) Flow chart of Implementation. b) p adaptivity algorithm for rigid cylinder problem with $k = 10$, $a = 0.5$ and $r = 4$, $\eta = 0.5\%$

0.2496% when the predefined error level is 0.5%. In addition, the p adaptivity scheme has successfully spotted the errors around 34%, which are indicated by red colour region in plot 4b.

5.0.1. Adaptivity schemes efficiency analysis

In the following numerical tests, we assessed plain h refinement ($p = 2$), uniform p enrichment and automatic p adaptivity, whilst fixed the mesh resolutions in descending order: $\tau_l = \frac{c p}{h_{max} f} = [8.6820, 5.7880, 5.2092, 4.9612, 4.3410, 3.4728, 3.0387, 2.7782]$ by varying h_{max} and f for h & p adaptivities respectively. h_{max} denotes maximum element size in mesh. As for the automatic p adaptivity, we replace p in τ_l by the average of p over whole computational domain. From both Figures, automatic p adaptivity delivers lowest error with decreasing resolution, and its efficiency has been guaranteed by less memories occupied compared to h adaptivity technique. but it requires more memories than uniform p adaptivity since it allocates more higher order elements based on error indicator. Overall, automatic p adaptivity with partly refined mesh is more stable than other adaptivity schemes since its natural of predefined error level, this fact can be observed from the plateau area of error (red solid line) in Figure 5a.

Figure 5: Automatic p adaptivity versus uniform h & p adaptivity based on mesh resolution τ_l , Impinging sound hard sphere problem, $a = 0.5$ and $r = 4$

6. Conclusions

Pertaining to the demand of efficient adaptivity method for solving high frequency acoustic problems, an object oriented a priori error estimator proposed by Prinn.A [1] has been implemented with both hierarchical Lobatto basis and generalized Duffy transformation. We omitted the plots of pollution error analysis (increasing domain length gradually), efficiency analysis (time, memory, no.DOFs), and effectivity indices in order to be concise in contexts. Although the a priori error estimator does not account for pollution effect, it enables to control the pollution effect within the frequency limit. Results shown the p adaptivity scheme based on a priori error estimator outperforms h & p adaptivity scheme in every aspects, while maintains the predefined error level within certain frequency band. This found of acoustic solver with p adaptivity have practical importance since in industrial applications, problems with high frequency sweeps are considered, it will be extremely expensive to refine the mesh within each frequencies and created a large number of meshes. On contrast, we can solve our problem with initial coarse mesh, and enrich our approximation basis in each frequencies.

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